

India paid no water fees at all. While these areas may have a plentiful supply of water (at least in the wet season), the opportunity cost of using this water for other purposes will rise as economic development proceeds, and it will become increasingly important to allocate water more efficiently. The current system of low prices at these sites appears to hinder such efficient allocation.

References

- Moya P, Hong L, Dawe D, Chen CD. 2001. Comparative assessment of on-farm water-saving irrigation techniques in the Zhanghe Irrigation System. In: Proceedings of the International Workshop on Water-Saving Irrigation for Paddy Rice, March 2001, Wuhan, China.
- Moya P, Dawe D, Pabale D, Tiongco M, Chien NV, Devarajan S, Djatiharti A, Lai NX, Niyomvit L, Ping HX, Redondo G, Wardana P. 2001. The economics of intensively irrigated rice in Asia. In: Dobermann A, Witt C, Dawe D, editors. Increasing productivity of intensive rice systems through site-specific nutrient management. Los Baños (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute and Eufield, N.J. (USA): Science Publishers Inc. (in press)

Farmers' participatory identification of gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason)-resistant rice varieties for desired characters

H.S. Singh, Central Horticultural Experiment Station, Indian Council for Agricultural Research (ICAR), Plandu, PO-Rajaulatu, Tata Road, Ranchi, Jharkhand; H.K. Awasti, and S.M. Kumar, Indira Gandhi Agricultural University (IGAU), Krishi Vigyan Kendra, PO-Pala, Balaghat, Madhya Pradesh, India

Rice is cultivated on 24,000 ha, mostly under rainfed conditions, with an average production of approximately 1.1 t ha⁻¹ in Balaghat District of Madhya Pradesh, India. The average annual rainfall in the district is 1,600 mm, with 70% occurring from mid-June to late September. Consequently, nearly 70% of the rice area under medium and low-lying conditions is transplanted. Being located near gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason)-prone areas such as Raipur and Sakoli, the rice crop in the district suffers almost every year from attacks from this pest. The state government of Madhya Pradesh had introduced gall midge-resistant varieties such as Asha, Surekha, and IR36. However, farmers stopped growing resistant varieties, except for IR36, after one or two cropping seasons because they did not meet their requirements. Consequently, susceptible varieties (e.g., Kranti, Kulture, MW10) possessing characteristics desired by

farmers were adopted. In recent years, heavy gall midge attacks in the district compelled farmers to look for resistant varieties with the desired characteristics.

To reduce losses caused by the pest, factors that contributed to gall midge incidence were pinpointed for appropriate intervention and resistant rice varieties with the desired characters were identified through a three-phase farmers' participatory program in the district by IGAU from 1994 to 1997.

Through brainstorming sessions, interactive group discussions, and matrix ranking with 123 farmers from 36 villages and 21 rural agricultural extension officers, the factors contributing to gall midge incidence were identified in the first phase of the program (Table 1). In the second phase, 11 rice varieties (resistant as well as local susceptible varieties as checks) were collected from IGAU and local farmers. These were grown and evaluated by 125 farmers at four growth

Table 1. Factors that farmers think contributed to gall midge incidence in rice.

Factors (in order of priority)	
1	Lack of resistant varieties with desired characters and use of susceptible varieties
2	Unbalanced use of fertilizers—i.e., high N, less P, and little or no K
3	Continuous rain from July to September, resulting in waterlogging and making insecticides ineffective
4	No direct seeding and late transplanting because of dependence on rain
5	Summer rice cultivation and late harvesting just before the onset of the next cropping season, leading to pest multiplication
6	Late and suboptimal dose of insecticides
7	No preventive control measures and lack of alternative control measures
8	Poor technical know-how and poor economic conditions to combat pest attack
9	Dependence on unskilled laborers

stages—tillering, panicle formation, milking, and maturity—and at postharvest for desired characters (Table 2). Farmers used evaluation sheets to rate the varieties. Scores for each variety at every evaluation stage were averaged. Based on these averages, six va-

rieties—Mahamaya, Baibhav, Kulture, R296-260, Abhaya, and Purnima—were selected by farmers (Table 3). Kulture was already being used by farmers, so the other five varieties were evaluated in farmers' fields in 10 villages in the third phase of the pro-

gram. These varieties were again evaluated for gall midge incidence, blast attack, grain filling, and yield. Despite its good yield potential, Abhaya was rejected in farmers' fields because of heavy blast incidence (40.2%); R296-260 was likewise rejected because of its high amount of chaffy grains (Table 3). On the basis of better performance, farmers selected and adopted varieties Mahamaya, Baibhav, and Purnima. Farmers multiplied seeds and distributed them through a farmer-to-farmer seed exchange program. Within two cropping seasons, farmers produced gall midge-resistant varieties.

Table 2. Farmers' preferred characters in a rice variety.

Characters
Gall midge-resistant
Duration is suitable for specific land types and water availability in the field
Can be sustained and yields better under water stress and biotic pressure
Tall enough to produce sufficient biomass for year-round cattle feeding, bundle making, transportation, and indoor storage
Stable yield—i.e., equal to or greater than that of existing varieties
Good market value—i.e., fit for flaked rice or parboiling
Easy threshing quality

Table 3. Performance of rice varieties evaluated by farmers.

Variety	Average score ^b	Gall midge incidence (% tillers infested)		Blast infection (% tillers infected)		Grain filling (%)		Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
		IGAU farm	Farmers' field	IGAU farm	Farmers' field	IGAU farm	Farmers' field	IGAU farm	Farmers' field
Mahamaya	4.07	0.5	0.4	5.5	10.2	86.0	87.5	4.2	4.1
Abhaya	3.94	0.8	0.8	12.5	40.2	80.2	80.6	3.6	3.5
Purnima	3.88	1.1	0.0	11.6	16.6	88.9	89.6	3.2	2.9
R321-49	3.72	6.5	—	6.5	—	73.6	—	3.2	—
R37-1	3.17	45.5	—	8.5	—	88.2	—	1.8	—
R-296-260	4.18	1.2	0.7	3.1	13.5	78.6	76.5	3.8	3.8
Kulture ^a	3.95	24.6	—	8.2	—	84.3	—	3.2	—
Kranti ^a	3.19	65.6	—	16.6	—	83.0	—	1.0	—
Ananda ^a	3.14	76.7	—	16.6	—	93.6	—	0.9	—
Baibhav	4.05	2.2	0.0	3.2	14.6	80.9	82.6	3.6	3.9
IR36 ^a	3.73	25.6	—	8.2	—	87.8	—	3.3	—

^aLocally available rice varieties. ^bAv score for desired characters. Scale used: 1–5, where 1 = low and 5 = high.

**IRRISTAT
Windows 4.0**

*Now available online
and on CD!*

IRRISTAT is a computer program for data management and basic statistical analysis of experimental data. It can be run in any 32-bit Windows operating system.

IRRISTAT has been developed primarily for analyzing data from agricultural field trials,

but many of the features can be used for analysis of data from other sources.

The main modules and facilities are Data management with a spreadsheet, Text editor, Analysis of variance, Regression, Genotype × environment interaction analysis, Quantitative trait analysis, Single site analysis, Pattern analysis, Graphics, and Utilities for randomization and layout, General factorial EMS, and Orthogonal polynomial.

The software (including tutorial in zip and pdf files) can be downloaded from the IRRI site at <http://www.cgiar.org/irri/irristat.htm>

The software is also available on CD for US\$19 for highly developed countries and \$5 for developing countries, with \$7 for handling costs.

Send suggestions, comments, or problems in using the software to

Biometrics

International Rice Research Institute
DAPO Box 7777
Metro Manila, Philippines
or e-mail: biometrics@irri.cgiar.org

To order a CD, e-mail: e.ramin@cgiar.org